

Hire-Smart: Automating Candidate Screening and Interview Analysis

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Abstract—Hiring is a tedious task for companies as they have to check each candidate's compability with the company and the number of candidates is increasing more and more.ATS systems try to minimize the HR work by using simple nlp techniques but this has cons too, such as candidate's rejection because they didnt use the exact matching keywords required for the job profile. To counter this issue,we propose a system named as hire-smart. We combined Large Language Models (LLMs) to parse resumes semantically and use multiple analysis tools(Open source libraries in python) to assess candidate in multiple levels. Instead of using simple analysis like parsing of candidate's answer , we focused on overall performance of the candidate like what expression do they have , are they stuttering or are they giving answers genuinely or not and then feed this data to the LLM to further assess the candidate's fitness for the company.We tested 100 resumes and 5-10 mock interviews achieving high accuracy for extraction of data from the resume and then analyzng the same skill's mentioned in the resume which reduces the time required for hiring drastically. The platform was built using FastAPI(backend),mongoDB(database) and React(frontend).

Index Terms—Artificial Intelligence, Natural Language Processing, Multimodal Analysis, Candidate Screening, Recruitment Automation, Emotion Detection, Full-Stack Development.

I. Introduction

HR departments have changed drastically after the advancement of the digital tools like linkdIn but this also increases the overhead of the candidates applying for the same job. This load on the HR deperatment makes them suscpetible to errors such as inducing biases while assessing candidates (for e.g. ranking a fair skinned person above a black skinned person or favor a male for a techincal work against a female).

Standard ATS handles volume volume but on the cost of failing promising candidates too. It is more like a boolean logic which either selects an applicant or rejects them. For example if a candidate is typing python as there skill in the resume but the company asks for specific framework he/she might get rejected even if they actually know the exact framework and this could have been easily known if

a human or AI were assessing the candidate instead of just a simple algorithmic ATS.

To tackle such issues we built the system which combines the two different parts of the hiring . first the resume screening part and the other the interiew process. To make sure that our backend is efficient for LLM usage, we kept the backend in python(fastApi) and react for frontend for its features in implementing the UI.

Our Contributions are as follows:

- 1) Semantic Parsing of resume: We used Gemini LLM to convert PDF resumes into clean JSON data avoiding using fine tuned model for each task to avoid overload, allowing us to capture meaning rather than just keywords.
- 2) Muiltple context : We took raw metrics from computer vision and audio analysis and passed them to the LLM. So that the model can generate more complex and accurate assessment of the candidate.
- 3) Asynchronous Audio Video process: Since the video analysis is slow ,we built a background worker system (using FastAPI) to handle task like ffmpeg transcodiing and deepface inference. This makes sure that the UI wont freeze while the users are using it. Also the compiled output of the interview would be visible once it has been asynchronously processed in the background.
- 4) NoSQL Data Storage: MongoDb can store data(documents) in varied ways in the same collection which makes it very good for handling assessment structures of different candidates which can vary drastically.

The rest of the paper covers the architecture,specific methodology, the results of our implementation, ethical concerns, and our plans for future updates respectively.

II. Related Work

A. The History of Resume Parsing

Previously, resume parsing was mostly based on Regex and predefined rules to pull data out of resume [1]. This worked fine for standard templates but broke down whenever a candidate used a complex layout. Later, researchers started using Conditional Random Fields and LSTMs[2]. These models were better at generalizing but required huge datasets of labeled resumes to learn from. Our approach avoids the need for labeled data entirely by using the reasoning abilities of modern GPT's, similar to recent trends in document intelligence[3].

B. Analyzing Interviews with AI

Assessing behavior has historically been a manual task. However, the field of Affective Computing has made it possible to automate the detection of facial micro-expressions. Tools like OpenSMILE [5] and DeepFace [7] have become the standard for pulling out audio and visual features. While some studies try to combine these features using weighted averages [6], we take it a step further. Instead of using fixed math weights, we use semantic interpretation. This means our AI can look at a long pauses and decide if it shows thoughtfulness or confusion based on the actual conversation context.

III. System Architecture

We built Hire-Smart with client- server architecture with different services in the server side as microservices, which helps keep the client and server side separated for logic and database and also makes it scalable.

A. Backend Service

The core application runs on FastAPI. We chose this over frameworks like Flask or Django specifically for its native async support. This is crucial for us because AI operations are I/O heavy, and we didn't want to block the server thread while processing. The backend is made using FastAPI because it comes with asynchronous I/O unlike Flask or Django and is becoming more of an industrial standard for AIML driven backends. Also validation of incoming data becomes easier using FastAPI's Pydantic which also helps in saving API tokens for bad requests.

1) Controller Logic: : The main backend code is separated from the routing and model code using different controllers for each of the different task as follows :

- resume_assessment_controller: Takes care of pdf uploads, text cleaning and managing the LLM parsing requests. 1
- interview_assess_controller: Handles the heavy video pipeline, including uploading, stripping audio and analyzing frames. 2
- job_controller: This allows the recruiters to post the jobs and also define the characteristics they are looking for in a candidate. 3

- 2) Database Choice:: Main reasons we used mongoDb:
- 1) Flexible Schema: As we know resumes are dynamic (Example: One person might list five projects and the other might list 10 interships) .Thus a document and collection model is more suitable for our task
- 2) LLM Output: The Ai model is instructed to output the data in json format and also the data taken from interview and resume is fed into the model in json format. This usage of semi-structured data makes it easy for the model to parse data and also the output json data can be easily mapped in the database reducing the reliance on usage of ORM or complex queries.

B. Frontend Application

The UI is built using React Library

- State: Auth context is used for sessions and jwt tokens.
- Feedback: Browser's MediaRecorder API is used to show candidates their video feed in real-time while also recording the same. This is done using hooks like useRef, useState and useEffect.
- Charts: Chart.js is used to map the probabilities across the timeline of the interview to provide analytical perspective.

Figure 1. Proposed architecture of the Hire-Smart platform highlighting the integration of external LLM services and internal ML models.

IV. Methodology

A. Pipeline A: Semantic Resume Analysis

The goal of this pipeline is to turn unstructured PDF's into a score that actually means something.

1) Extracting Text:: We processed uploaded files using pdfplumber. Custom logic to loop through the pages and avoiding headers and footers(which are just noise comparatively). The raw text is then fed to the AI.

2) Structuring the Data: Rather than training a specific Named Entity Recognition model, we use prompt engineering with Google's Gemini-2.5-Flash. We constrain the system prompt to force a specific JSON output. The prompt looks something like this:

```
prompt = """
You are an expert AI Resume Parser.
Analyze the following text and return a strict JSON.
Required Fields:
- skills: list of technical skills
- experience: list of objects {role, company, duration}
- education: list of objects {degree, college}
- missing keywords: compared to Job Description
"""
```

Such system prompts helps the model to capture only the skills implied by the candidate. So if a candidate mentions using the CI/CD pipelines , it can be inferred that the candidates also knows git and github even if it not directly mentioned in the resume.

B. Pipeline B: Interview Assessment

Three different data sources are combined here in this pipeline:1. visual data(how they look), audio data(how they sound and text (what words they are speaking).

1) Handling Video Asynchronously: Video processing is slow as a 7 minutes of interview can take couple of minutes (if GPU is used). So to stop HTTP request from timing out ,this task is managed by the FastAPI's "Background Tasks".

- 1) The user takes interview-> video gets uploaded->server saves it->returns 202 response code.
- 2) In the background ffmpeg is then used to separate audio and input it to a .wav file and frames are extracted at the rate of 1 frames/second.
- 3) When finished the database status updates to completed.

2) Feature Extraction: Visual: In the video's frame,the deepface model is used to extract faces(this is one of the main reason video processing is slow).But this is important as it shows the range of emotions like happy ,sad or neutral and the one with the highest probability is selected as the main emotion.

Audio: Standard Speech-Recognition library was used to convert the audio into text to check the answer of the candidate.

3) Fusing Metrics with LLM: The scoring of the candidate is not done using a formula rather subjective context is provided to the model/LLM to judge candidate

We feed the LLM data such as:

- Speaking Rate: words per minute (wpm).
- Emotions: e.g.,Neutral: 0.6, Happy: 0.3, Fear: 0.1.
- Text: The text taken from the audio.

The Model then compares it with the criteria already set in the prompts like if the speaking rate passes the threshold of 160wpm then fear is detected or if the speaking rate is less than 160 and greater than 100 then it is detected as neutral speech rate thus adding it as a variable to the candidates interview analysis.

V. Implementation Results

A. Setup

The setup consisted of the following dataset:

- Resumes: 100 resumes of individual from engineering fields.
- Videos: few mock interviews (5 interviews with 2-10 minutes of duration).
- Hardware: A local pc with 8GB RAM. GPU:Nvidia gtx 1650.

Figure 2. UML diagrams: sequence diagram showing the interactions between the recruiter, the backend system, and AI models.

Table I
Resume Field Extraction Accuracy

Field	Precision	Recall
Contact Info	1.00	1.00
Education	0.99	0.99
Skills	0.96	0.98
Experience	0.94	0.92

B. Parsing Accuracy

Manual review of each of the following fields of different resumes used for the project:

Table I shows that structured fields are very accurate.The "Experience" field scored slightly lower, mostly because some resumes use non-standard layouts where dates are far apart from job titles.

C. Latency

We timed the video pipeline to see how long it takes:

- Frame Extraction: 0.2s per second of video.
- Emotion Inference: 15-20 frames per second resulting in 1x-1.2x time required (NOTE:better GPU would have higher performce likely resulting in 0.5x time required).
- Overall: The system runs at about the same real-time speed. A 5-minute video takes roughly take 5 minutes to analyze.

D. Comparison vs. Traditional ATS

We compared Hire-Smart against a baseline Keyword-Matching system.

Table II
Comparison with Traditional ATS

Feature	Traditional ATS	Hire-Smart (Ours)
Matching Logic	Exact Keyword	Semantic Context
Ranking	Boolean Count	LLM Reasoning
Interview Analysis	None	Multimodal (A/V/Text)
Explanation	None	Textual Justification

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Figure 3. UI Output displaying candidate scores and emotion distribution over time.

VI. Ethical Considerations and Limitations

A. Bias in Algorithms

AI in recruitment has a high risk of reinforcing bias. As shown by the referenced paper[8], facial recognition often struggles with accuracy with different demographics. We use pre-trained models like DeepFace, but we haven't performed a full fairness audit on our specific pipeline yet. Because of this, the emotion recognition feature should be treated as a helper signal and not a definitive filter.

B. Privacy

Storing voice, facial data means we have to be very careful about privacy laws. Currently, we only store video data while the session is active, and we recommend using encryption-at-rest for any real-world deployment.

C. Hallucinations

Generative models sometimes "hallucinate," resulting in misevaluation of the candidate. We try to stop this by instructing the prompt to strictly output NULL if information is not found but human review is still necessary.

VII. Conclusion and Future Work

Our project shows the combination of GENAI with computer-vision can make the recruitment process easier and faster. Also ATS like technology is replaced by more semantical resume parsers making the assessment more human like and forgiving.

Future work includes the following :

- 1) Proctoring: Adding checks to ensure candidates aren't using their own native AI tools to cheat during interview.
- 2) Client-Side AI: Running the emotion inference model to directly run on the client side avoiding load on the central server. This improves privacy and saves server costs.
- 3) Live Streaming: Updating the pipeline to support WebSockets as it would allow for real time feedback on multiple interviews at once.